

WHAT ARE MASCULINIST VALUES IN ORGANISATIONS?

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A critical evaluation of the impact of masculine values in an organisation on female employees career

“Further, and in contrast to the equal opportunities stance of which organizational liberal feminism forms an important strand, there is also a growing body of work around the need to manage what has become known as diversity in the workplace - to be responsible for and sensitive to the different types of individuals who make up an organization. Gender is an important topic in diversity, as are race, ethnicity, class, disability and HIV status, as well as other issues less prominent in the equal opportunities literature, such as personality, value systems, work style, religion, lifestyle, education level and so on.”

(Fulop and Linstead, p. 55).

Managing Diversity effectively is often a fruitful process in the management of contemporary enterprises. However, some might argue that much of the literature neglects to acknowledge the masculinist values that pervade organisations.

What are masculinist values in organisations? Critically evaluate how they might impede the quality of working life and career ambitions of female employees?

Masculine values and how it affects women in the workplace

INTRODUCTION

According to Robbins (1981: 591) "For years, woman and minorities have been victims of discrimination, often placing the blame on white males for keeping them out of jobs and power positions."

This is supported by Adler and Izraeli (1994b: 89) who state that although woman represent more than 50 % of the world population, in no country do woman represent half or even close to half of the corporate managers.

In the 21st century the career growth of woman are still greatly suppressed by masculinist values. Man, like most of

his predecessors, delegate women to a position subordinate to themselves because of their role in reproduction. They assume women are inferior to them because nature has delegated to women the simple task of bearing and nurturing children. And men went out of their way to make sure that women did not become politically active or overly educated.

“A woman's natural role is to bare and care for children, while man's natural role is to support and protect his family. The task of a man requires intelligence. He must think of ways to provide the basic necessities for his family (food, shelter, etc.) and shield his offspring from danger. The intellectual ability of men increased because they used logic and reason to survive. Nature requires less from a woman because her role in procreation is purely physical. Neither the formation of the child inside of her womb nor the production of milk in her breast is dependent on a female's ability to think. Because women did not exercise their gray matter, their minds evolved at a much slower rate than their male counterparts.” - **Darwin.**

Herbert Spenser, an evolutionist, even believed that women lacked in the ability to reason and comprehend general principals because they were the latest characteristics passed on to man from evolution.

Traditionally a culture of male dominance and female subservience has existed as far back as recorded history. This has been based largely on physical strength, which has led to a subconscious yet misleading acceptance, by female species that this physical advantage automatically lends itself to a mental and emotional advantage.

Until the early 19th century, male dominance had not been questioned by females nor was individual strengths and weaknesses gauged i.e. who was the best person for the job not the best man. **See Annexure 1 for Details**

Cultural diversity in organisations is a concept that is currently evolving as more industries move towards a global marketplace. It is viewed that every human being has equal worth, is entitled to the same privileges and opportunities, without regard to race, gender, age or disability. This view has led to changes in management practices relating to recruitment, training and education of employees. However, cultural differences cannot be managed away and masculinist views can and do still impede the quality of working life and career ambitions for female employees. There are various hidden barriers that contribute towards this impediment for example, if you go back in history, many cultures and historical periods have taken the domination of women by men for granted, as part of the natural order of things. Remnants of such thoughts are found when certain practices, which deny women their full human value, are described as “ancient customs” or “long cultural traditions”.

This document will evaluate the effects of some of the masculine values on women in the workplace.

What are masculinist values in organizations?

Masculine Values

See Annexure 2 for Details

It is important to note that in this discussion "gender" is seen as a social construct, referring to the stereotype gender behaviour, namely female and male leadership styles or stereotypical masculine and feminine leadership styles, which is socially constructed behaviour, influenced by culture, and is learned and thus gender behaviour. In this regard, however, it is important to note the following:

- The terms "masculinity" and "femininity" are relative and not absolute terms: a man can behave in a feminine way and a woman can behave in a masculine way; this merely means they would be deviating from

certain conventions in their own society.

- Also, individual women can learn to function in a masculine way and individual men in a feminine way.

'What were once claimed to be manly virtues (heroism, independence, courage, strength, rationality, will, backbone, virility) have become masculine vices (abuse, destructive aggression, coldness, emotional inarticulacy, detachment). Advocates of the anti-masculine culture are particularly disdainful of the alleged inability of men to "ask for help" and "display emotion".' (The End of Masculinity, J MacInnes, p45)

Under the original backing of organisational management (Whyte, 1956), gender was not an issue. Gender inequality is nothing new, both paid and unpaid forms of work consistently exhibit patterns of inequality. Analyses illustrate the way jobs are immutably assigned to one sex or the other (e.g. McEwen, 1990). Here only men were considered breadwinners, with women's role to supplement income (Milkman, 1987). For example, the traditional image, and one gaining a new start now with employers, was that employees put in extra effort beyond the paid cycle. Organisational management supports the workaholic, which does not allow for the other responsibilities in the lives of women. Analysis has traditionally viewed discrimination of women employees through both horizontal and vertical divisions of labor. This viewpoint argues that is more likely that a man will move to the top of the ladder. Traditionally it is assumed that women are excluded from the benefits of a core workforce (Jenkins and Buswell, 1994). Women workers have in general been separated from the predominantly male culture of organisations. According to Davies, 1990, the feminine gender identity at work has been suppressed. Women managers are often required to exhibit what is almost a male gender identity, and are habitually viewed as exceptions to women in general (cf. Hearn and Parkin, 1991). This is not helped by the poor emphasis organisations give to the detail of women's lives e.g. day-care facilities, paternity leave, etc.

Feminine values

See Annexure 2 for Details

Feminine values include the manner in which women address and view various areas. These views encompass moral reasoning that emphasize relationships, interdependence, connection, body, emotions, nature, peace and life. These work towards women using different strategies to deal with issues that arise than what men would.

In the past, traditional western ethics have depreciated as well as devalued women's moral experience. It has been viewed that traditional western ethics (Jagger, "Feminist Ethics," 1992) fail women in five particular areas, namely:

- It shows little concern for women's interests and rights
- It dismisses as morally uninteresting the problems that arise in the home environment (caring for children, cooking, cleaning etc.)
- It suggests that women are not as morally developed as men
- It overvalues masculine traits like independence, reason, culture and undervalues feminine traits like interdependence, community nature etc.
- It favors masculine ways of moral reasoning that emphasize rules, and impartiality over feminine ways of moral reasoning.

The “Glass Ceiling Effect”

Over the years, the term “the glass ceiling effect” has come to describe the invisible barrier that block women from top positions within organisations. The term “glass ceiling” was first used in 1986 by two Wall Street Journal reporters who described a corporate world where women were blocked from obtaining top positions in a company because of tradition and prejudice. They wrote that “the executive suite seemed within their grasp, but they just couldn’t break through the top.”(Carol Hymowitz and Timothy Schellhardt, Special Report on The Corporate Women) Among the reasons cited for the existence of the “glass ceiling” is the belief that women are drawn away from obtaining top positions because of family responsibilities, stereotypes about women not being able to function in the tough corporate world.

There are barriers causing the under representation of women in organisation with predominantly male power structures (Morrison, White, & Van Velsor, 1987; Jones, 1986; Nkomo & Cox, 1989). For example, data from the Quality of Employment Panel on career measures of men and women revealed that women were held to higher promotion standards than men and received fewer promotions than men with equal measured abilities (Olson & Becker, 1983).

This "Glass ceiling effect" became very apparent when conducting my research interviews with delegates attending my IT Project Management Workshop. I have noticed that over the past eight year the course constitution based on an average of fifty delegates per workshop, and three workshops per year has moved from being ninety percent males and ten percent females to seventy percent females and thirty percent males in this IT Project management field. This has put pressure on me to change my presentation style, especially the jokes I tell as well as the illustrations used. This has been a major "cultural shock" and adjustment period for me. **See annexure 3 for interview details**

Masculine Leadership Styles and the impact on feminine values

Men and women have traditionally had different leadership styles. In our opinion, these differences partly come about because women do not exhibit the same power and dominance that men do in any given circumstance.

Men are more likely to use power based on organisational position or formal authorities while women assign power to personal characteristics like charisma, interpersonal skills, hard work and personal contacts (Rosener, 1990).

Eisler (1991) who examined models of social organisation worldwide and through time concluded that Western societies function under the “dominator” model. The dominator philosophy is about rankings, hierarchies with emphasis on the use of “power-over” to control the environment. It is associated with masculine values of toughness, conquest and domination. In contrast, the “partnership” value is characterized by valuing difference.

Leadership style varies with a manager's attitude to power. Feminist concepts of power include "power-to" and "power-with" in contrast to "power-over". Feminism illustrates an attitude to power that values its sharing rather than hoarding. It encompasses a belief that individuals who share power in a group can yield a result more valuable than the sum of the parts. To bring these new bases of power into management may be to witness how they can supplement a woman's leadership, thus using in a positive and conscious way the synergy between personal sources of power and her own position power (Ragins and Sundstrom, 1989).

Compatibility of styles based on value systems

Men and women's communication styles have always varied in that women prefer to have support and confirmation of their opinions and beliefs whereas men don't really feel this is necessary. Women have a well-known reputation for being more emotional than men. In the following paragraphs, the reasons for this will be looked at in more detail.

It has been argued that differences between men and women in communication styles are a result of gender differences in childhood experiences and the use of language in those experiences. For example, young boys and girls spend most of their playtime within their own gender groups with boys tending towards a definite status structure and acknowledged winners and losers whereas girls play in small groups or in pairs where there are no winners or losers. (Deborah Tannen, 1990)

Differences in Communication Styles			
Men		Women	
1	Conversations are negotiations in which people seek the upper hand in a hierarchical social order	1	Conversations are negotiations for closeness in which people seek to share support and reach consensus
2	Communication emphasizes independence.	2	Communication emphasizes intimacy.
3	Inclined to resist doing what he is asked to do; perceives requests as orders	3	Inclined to do what she is asked to do; does not perceive requests as orders.
4	Talk is for information	4	Talk is for interaction.

(Source: Adapted from Deborah Tannen, 1990)

An example of how gender differences in communication are manifested is the manner in which men and women identify problems in and out of the workplace. Women will identify a problem and attempt to solicit confirmation, support and a discussion of the problem where a man will often respond to a strong piece of advice on how to solve the problem. This leads to a communication breakdown between men and women due to misunderstandings in the communication of the problem because the male colleague responds to the problem in a manner in which the female colleague interprets his response as telling her what to do. The communication breakdown can be a result of men not realizing that they are using their power to inadvertently block someone else's perspective. The male colleague may wonder if she lacks the confidence to solve the problem herself. This view can be detrimental to a female employee especially if the male colleague is her boss. The high potential for career damage from such misunderstandings is very clear; because of this it is important that both parties understand the differences in order to achieve maximum effectiveness of interaction in the working environment.

Men and women often react differently to situations. This degree of difference is often the result of the experiences of men and women within the division of labor that prevails in society at any time. For example, the experience of working at home influences human personality in ways that are drastically different to life on a construction site. However, the differences in these experiences do not lead men and women to develop genuinely contrasting emotions. It is not so much that women are emotional and men are not, but rather that their feelings are expressed through different social conventions.

Organisational Management Role

Changing structures in organisations have a fundamental impact on the role of management. While a traditional manager deciphers the goals of the organisation into tasks for departments and workers, the growth of the information economy has meant a broadening of the management role. No longer operating through control backed up by authority within the organisation, Managers must become leaders (Kanter, 1989). The leader must express a vision for the organisation that can be clearly translated into tasks for the specialists in a flatter organisation. The roles of manager and worker are shifting. "Work' is what goes on inside people's heads; it is almost impossible to supervise". (Naisbett and Aburdene, 1990)

According to Maccoby (1990) a second change in values is evident in what people want from work and in how it will fit into their lives. The new focus is on independence and self-development in wanting a balanced life, consisting of both work and family. The new corporate philosophy places a value on balance. Recognizing that happy employees give a greater return to their organisation, it is a holistic approach to business.

Using the terms of Handy (1989), an organisation that is a "feminist" organisation is a learning organisation, which will cope successfully with change. It is also a "caring organisation" in which each member is constantly learning, in an atmosphere of celebration of achievement and corporate forgiveness.

Quality management has begun to emphasize the importance of redistributing power within organisations. "Empowerment may not be the most important tool, but it is certainly a very powerful way of tapping into the talent within an organisation which otherwise might go unutilized" (Hand, 1993).

The authors Helgesen (1990) and Loden (1985) emphasize the importance of paying attention to relationships both within the organisation and outside it. By doing this, managers ensure that information flows in all directions and simultaneously employees feel valued within the organisation. With this information comes responsibility, which is seen as part of the process of "ownership" of the work by an individual. This is strongly linked to the concept of empowerment.

How does the type of organization affect women?

Looking at the business world today, it is possible to categorize management styles as follows:

I. Authoritarian Style

This style can be defined as being coercive and employees are expected to recognize his authority. This type of manager must win at all costs in order to impress others. They will rather find flaws in the work that has been done and will never think of praising anyone for a job well done. It is important for them to control everyone by restricting activities that have not been sanctioned by them. They motivate by using threats of disciplinary action and are forceful, dominant and vengeful.

II. Compliant Style

This type of manager is too scared to "come out of his box". They cannot stand the thought having to take a stand just in case things turn out badly, so he won't be blamed. They put on a compliant face to their superiors but will be rigid and inflexible when it comes to their employees.

III. Developmental Style

This type of manager motivates their employees by praising and educating and allowing them to take responsibility for their actions, whether right or wrong. They see errors as a learning curve and a major means of acquiring experience. They will have regular appraisals and set achievable goals.

Corporate culture within an organisation contributes to these various styles in that the management style is reflected by the culture within the organisation.

Corporate culture can be viewed as the underlying belief systems within an organisation. Organisational culture focuses on values as the primary element. A large part of any organisation's culture consists of the cultural mindsets that people use to evaluate appropriateness of business behavior. (Geoffrey James, 1988) The perception of a manager's role in a company is largely dependant on the corporate culture. It is the culture that symbolically and factually expresses the message the company wants to convey (mission and philosophy).

This culture emphasizes an environment in which people collaborate on their work, through working in teams and across functions. It is reflected in the value placed on skills such as negotiation and facilitation - the building of bridges rather than of divisions. Women engage a participative style in sharing power and information, encouraging participation, and self-inclusion in a group identity. Rosener describes this as more of an "interactive" style that can be viewed as a concentration on enhancing the self-worth of others due to a belief that to do so is a win-win situation for both manager and others; energizing others to make work both challenging and fun. Rosener believes that to motivate, inspire, and energize others are important leadership qualities and enthusiasm important.

Growth and Promotion possibilities

Despite these changes in organisational structures and attitudes, there still seems to be a substantial gap between the theory of a good organisational culture and the implementation of it in many organisations. This gap can be seen by a survey that was done by Coates in 1997. The results yielded some interesting results in several areas including the traditional perceptions that women are not capable of being effective managers opposing traditional masculine driven organisational values. Some extracts of this survey illustrate some interesting truths about females and management styles.

Gender also has a significant effect on chances for promotion even after career relevant factors such as formal education were controlled (Cannings, 1988). Some studies have also found that women enter organisations at significantly lower levels than their male counterparts with the same qualification and years of experience. It has also been found that the entry level has a significant impact on career success in the future. The following graph taken from a study that was conducted by Coates in 1997 outlines other factors that prevent women from progressing up the corporate ladder.

Barriers to Women Progressing at Work

Organisations may be thought of, as having their own distinctive cultures and the fit between the organisation and individual culture is important to the career outcomes of individuals within the organisation.

Some researchers have stressed that value differences between men and women are relatively minor (Powell, 1988; Epstein, 1988), while others argue that the value differences are significant (Henning & Jardim, 1976; Gilligan, 1982;

Helgesen, 1990).

The following quotation is illustrative of the view that ranking of women will be lower than men:

“Dichotomous distinctions rarely avoid creating ranked comparisons, and in the case of female-male, whatever characteristics are ascribed to each gender, those associated with men rank higher” (Epstein, 1988, pg 233).

These views have a distinct effect on a women’s success with her career because the underlying bias of setting higher standards for women with regards to promotions as well as her lower entry level within the organisation.

New trends in organizations and the affect on women in the workplace

Today's anti-masculine culture condemns forms of behavior that in the past were considered elementary human virtues. Critics of masculinity have a strong distaste for the habit of self-reliance and self-control. They believe that the aspiration for heroism is ludicrous. And they are intensely suspicious of the virtues of independence, willpower, risk-taking and rationality.

Research has continually questioned the assumption that there are qualitative differences between men and women. However, researchers have emphasized that there are greater differences within one sex than between them. For instance, although most commentators uncritically accept the contention that boys find it more difficult than girls to confide in friends, research suggests that such differences across the gender line are very small.

Summary

What we are dealing with here is not a question of women against men or men against women. Rather, it is a question of social organisation. What has been described until now are ways of looking at women, men, work and power that by and large conform to what has been termed a “dominator model” of society. In other words, a way of structuring human relations where, beginning with the ranking of one-half of humanity over the other, the primary organising principle is ranking of men over women, men over men, nation over nation, man over nature or employer over employee.

Four decades ago, Whyte (1956) described how a new human expression had become universally evident. This was the notion of the “Organisational Man”; an early corporate culture characterised by the middle ranks of managers in large organisations, who were subject to a “social ethic”. Under the original conception, gender was not an issue. However, in a contemporary view of human resource management and corporate culture, it has become crucial to understanding both notions of competitive advantage and the thesis and influence of commitment both in the literature and the workplace.

Analysis has traditionally viewed discrimination of woman employees through both horizontal and vertical divisions of labour. This perspective argues it is likely to be the men who move to the top of the ladder. Traditionally therefore, it is assumed that women are excluded from the benefits of a core workforce. However, a study at present has highlighted some ‘significant’ improvements in the position of women within both large and small organisations and questions the very notion of a separate corporate culture identity, but not gender inequality. Corporate culture has the power to strip away traditional masculine identities associated with work.

Conclusion

Even though there is a definite trend in most organisations to embrace the concepts of an adaptive and non-hierarchical culture, which favor female management and emotional behavior, it is clear that the gap between theory and practice still needs to be closed before it can be said that the quality of and career ambitions of a female are not impeded. The traditional, bureaucratic styles within organisations contribute to this because the culture within the organisation can have an affect on the management style used and their views about women in the organisation. There is a trend in smaller companies and in some industries where women are slowly starting to gain promotions and move up the “corporate ladder” e.g. information technology environment and projects.

It can be deduced that, for woman to succeed in the corporate environment and have a successful work / life balance is an extremely tough task. It would seem that they need to prove themselves at all times and therefore need to work longer hours and deny aspects of their personalities. One result of this is that family issues are neglected. They not only need to work longer, but harder and smarter as well. In South Africa it is, however, evident that times are changing as a result of the Employment Equity Act and the fact that management is being made more aware of the positive influence that female employees have on their colleagues, both subordinate and on a par. Thereby increasing job satisfaction, productivity and organisational success.

Annexure 1: The Evolution of Women Rights

The statement that men have suppressed women is confirmed throughout history. It all started with the caveman. Women were totally dominated: “Pulled by the hair”. In the medieval times, men were heroes and fought battles while woman were owned, and treaded like slaves. This world trend still continues today in the eastern countries where, for example, woman can only eat after the men eaten.

During the later centuries though, this perception started to fade and women now a days stand up for their rights, just look at all the feminist movements today. But the evolution of women rights did not come easily. American history motivates this statement.

Year	Development
1776	Abigail Adams writes to her husband, John Adams, asking him to "remember the ladies" in the new code of laws. Adams replies the men will fight the "despotism of the petticoat."
1777	Women lose the right to vote in New York.
1780	Women lose the right to vote in Massachusetts.
1784	Women lose the right to vote in New Hampshire.
1787	US Constitutional Convention places voting qualifications in the hands of the states. Women in all states except New Jersey lose the right to vote.
1792	Mary Wollstonecraft publishes <i>Vindication of the Rights of Women</i> in England.
1807	Women lose the right to vote in New Jersey, the last state to revoke the right.
1830s	Formation of the female anti-slavery associations

1836	Angelina Grimke appeals to Southern women to speak out against slavery.
1837	The "Pastoral Letter of the General Association of Massachusetts to the Congregational Churches Under Their Care" is promulgated against women speaking in public against slavery, it is mainly directed against the Grimke sisters.
1840	World Anti-Slavery Convention in London. Lucretia Mott, Elizabeth Cady Stanton, and other women barred from participating on account of their sex.
1848	First Women's Rights convention in Seneca Fall, New York. Equal suffrage proposed by Elizabeth Cady Stanton After debate of so radical a notion, it is adopted.
1850	Women's rights convention held in April in Salem, Ohio. First national women's rights convention held in October in Worcester, Massachusetts.
1850-1861	Annual Women's Rights conventions held. The last, in 1861, in Albany, New York lobbies for a liberalized divorce bill. Horace Greely opposes the bill, which loses.
1861-1865	Civil War. Over the objections of Susan B. Anthony, women put aside suffrage activities to help the war effort.
1867	Fourteenth amendment passes Congress, defining citizens as "male;" this is the first use of the word male in the Constitution. Kansas campaign for black and woman suffrage: both lose. Susan B. Anthony forms Equal Rights Association, working for universal suffrage.
1868	Fourteenth amendment ratified. Fifteenth amendment passes Congress, giving the vote to black men. Women petition to be included but are turned down. Formation of New England Woman Suffrage Association. In New Jersey, 172 women attempt to vote; their ballots are ignored.
1869	Frederick Douglass and others back down from woman suffrage to concentrate on fight for black male suffrage. National Woman Suffrage Association formed in May with Elizabeth Cady Stanton as president. American Woman Suffrage Association formed in November with Henry Ward Beecher as president. In England, John Stuart Mill, economist and husband of suffragist Harriet Taylor, publishes <i>On the Subjugation of Women</i> . Wyoming territory grants first woman suffrage since 1807.
1870	Fifteenth Amendment ratified. The Grimke sisters, now quite aged, and 42 other women attempt to vote in Massachusetts, their ballots are cast but ignored. Utah territory grants woman suffrage.
1871	The Anti-Suffrage Society is formed.
1872	Susan B. Anthony and supporters arrested for voting. Anthony's sisters and 11 other women held for \$500 bail. Anthony herself is held for \$1000 bail.
1873	Denied a trial by jury, Anthony loses her case in June and is fined \$100 plus costs. Suffrage demonstration at the Centennial of the Boston Tea Party.
1874	Protest at a commemoration of the Battle of Lexington. In <i>Myner v. Happerstett</i> the US Supreme Court decides that being a citizen does not guarantee suffrage. Women's Christian Temperance Union formed.

1876	On July 4, in Philadelphia, Susan B. Anthony reads The Declaration for the Rights of Women from a podium in front of the Liberty Bell. The crowd cheers. Later, the suffragists meet in the historic First Unitarian Church.
1878	Woman suffrage amendment first introduced in US Congress.
1880	Lucretia Mott, born in 1793, dies.
1882	The House and Senate appoint committees on woman suffrage, both report favorably.
1884	Belva Lockwood runs for president. The US House of Representatives debates woman suffrage.
1886	Women protest being excluded from the dedication ceremonies for the Statue of Liberty. Suffrage amendment reaches the US Senate floor; it is defeated two to one.
1887	Utah women lose right to vote.
1890	The NWSA and the AWSA merge to form NAWSA. The focus turns to working at the state level. Campaign loses in South Dakota.
1893	Matilda Joslyn Gage publishes <i>Woman, Church and State</i> . After a vigorous campaign led by Carrie Chapman Catt, Colorado men vote for woman suffrage.
1894	Despite 600,000 signatures, a petition for woman suffrage is ignored in New York. Lucy Stone, born in 1818, dies.
1895	Elizabeth Cady Stanton publishes <i>The Woman's Bible</i> . Utah women regain suffrage.
1896	Idaho grants woman suffrage.
1900	Carrie Chapman Catt takes over the reins of the NASWA.
1902	Elizabeth Cady Stanton, born in 1815, dies.
1906	Susan Brownell Anthony, born in 1820, dies.
1907	Harriet Stanton Blatch, Elizabeth's daughter, forms the Equality League of Self Supporting Women, which becomes the Women's Political Union in 1910. She introduces the English suffragists' tactics of parades, street speakers, and pickets.
1910	Washington (state) grants woman suffrage.
1911	California grants woman suffrage. In New York City, 3,000 march for suffrage.
1912	Teddy Roosevelt's Progressive Party includes woman suffrage in their platform. Oregon, Arizona, and Kansas grant woman suffrage.
1913	Women's Suffrage parade on the eve of Wilson's inauguration is attacked by a mob. Hundreds of women are injured, no arrests are made. Alaskan Territory grants suffrage. Illinois grants municipal and presidential but not state suffrage to women.
1916	Alice Paul and others break away from the NASWA and form the National Women's Party.
1917	Beginning in January, NWP posts silent "Sentinels of Liberty" at the White House. In June, the arrests begin.

	Nearly 500 women are arrested, 168 women serve jail time, some are brutalized by their jailers. North Dakota, Indiana, Nebraska, and Michigan grant presidential suffrage; Arkansas grants primary suffrage. New York, South Dakota, and Oklahoma state constitutions grant suffrage.
1918	The jailed suffragists released from prison. Appellate court rules all the arrests were illegal. President Wilson declares support for suffrage. Suffrage Amendment passes US House with exactly a two-thirds vote but loses by two votes in the Senate.
1919	In January, the NWP lights and guards a "Watchfire for Freedom." It is maintained until the Suffrage Amendment passes US Senate on June 4. The battle for ratification by at least 36 states begins.
1920	The Nineteenth Amendment, called the Susan B. Anthony Amendment, is ratified by Tennessee on August 18. It becomes law on August 26.

Table 1. Evolution of the Female American Suffrage.

Adapted from: Bernstein, J., Coté-Bonanno, J. , Reilly, L., Carver, J., and Doremus, M. (1996).

ANNEXURE 2: Table comparing masculine and Feminist Values

Masculinist Values	Feminist Values
1. Goal-orientated, narrow focus.	1. Energetic & enthusiastic, able to generate excitement
2. Analytical	2. Communicate expectations
3. Focus on performance, emphasises facts.	3. Keep people informed
4. Uses power and position to obtain objectives.	4. Give feedback
5. Competitive	5. Competitive (for group / family)
6. Leader as Master type attitude	6. Assertive (in a leadership position)
7. Dominant	7. Set high standards for themselves
8. Exclusive	8. Set high standards for others
9. Individualistic	9. People orientated
10. Less self disclosing	10. Caring, nurturing
11. Willingness to take risks	11. Creative
12. Open to new ideas	12. Seeks connection, affinity
13. Charismatic	13. Multi-tasking skills
14. Vertical and hierarchical	14. Verbal
15. Rational and objective: emphasis facts and tasks, "one right way."	15. Gentle, non-confrontational
16. Communicate to overpower, to strategise power	16. Family priorities
17. Retains and builds own power & knowledge	17. Naïve, pure, easily manipulated
18. Unemotional	18. Emotional

Source: Adapted from Booyesen and Beaty (1997), Kotter (1996), Bennis and Ward (1998), Parkin (1991), Davies (1990), Wilson (1995)

Annexure 3: Interviews conducted in Johannesburg South Africa By myself (Dennis mark Laxton) during March -April 2000

(A sample of some key responses are attached)

Target Audience based on delegates attending my IT project management workshop

Interview 1 - Married female with 1 child - Executive Consultant in IT industry

1) What in your opinion is "masculinist culture" and can you identify some "masculinist values"?

I understand this as being a work culture, which centres around men - their needs, their values, their priorities. It would exclude the fact that woman have value to add in a work environment, but have to balance this with the needs of their home. In any relationship (or the ones that I know), the woman is the person who sorts out the house, the maid, the gardner, the food, the bills, takes the kid to the doctor or dentist, rushes home should any crisis occur. The fact that she may be a major breadwinner in the family does not reduce her responsibilities in the home. The culture in many work environments does not recognise this (at best) or frowns upon your home responsibilities and how this could potentially impact your ability to deliver at work (at worst). As a result - a woman will be looked a twice when a promotion opportunity comes up ("Is she going to rush off and fall pregnant and leave us in the dwang" was something I had to answer to when I applied for a big promotion at work). Let's put this in context - in the bad old days of apartheid, our "boys" HAD to do annual army duties - 1 month to 3 months off per annum. Were any of them discriminated against because of this? No! Were they paid a third of their salaries while doing army duty? In many cases No!

In addition, men have a ideal of what a woman is like - caring, emotional, soft etc.etc Therefore when they come across a woman in the work environment who is assertive, she would be referred to as aggressive. When they deal with a woman who puts forward her viewpoint passionately, she would be referred to as emotional.

Men's values (note that because I am listing these under men, does not mean that they do not also apply to women. However, because of other responsibilities detailed above, a woman has to learn to balance things):

Success, Power, Authority

As apposed to woman who may have the same values but these are tempered with Home.

2) Is it a concern in your work (current and or historic) environment? If so, why?

I have had a few experiences of the masculinist culture:

- have been called aggressive
- have been told to stop being emotional
- when I raised issues about my job content and level of authority was told a) this isn't a little girl's job, you know and b) you're feeling insecure.
- had to justify if I did fall pregnant how this would impact my ability to deliver the job's requirements my boss was formally recognised as the success to the IT Manager at "Company A". When he resigned did she get the post ? Nope - a man was brought in. The reasons were justified till the cows came home, but for her the glass ceiling was so apparent that she was left with no option other than leaving.
- a friend of mine (Professional Civil Engineer) gets paid less than her male colleagues

3) Have you any personal experiences that you would like to share.

See point 1

4) How does "masculinist values" impede on the quality of your working life and in your career ambitions?

I would love to go back into consulting but I cannot (note : not at "Company B" !!!). Because of my home commitments I cannot (rather will not) do out of town assignments. Consulting firm I applied to said this was a "killer concern".

Other than that, I have not found my career progress inhibited because I am a woman. I have had to justify things that perhaps a man would not have, but we woman work in a "masculinist" culture, so it's to be expected - not so ?! I have learnt to balance things, and juggle priorities. Despite what I said in 1, my husband is an enormous help. Without his support, I would never be able to succeed.

5) What changes (if any) would you make to your organisational culture to better manage gender diversity?

difficult one. Let me think more and I'll feedback to you later

6) Comments

Haven't I said enough ?

Interview 2 - Single female with 2 children - Manager in IT industry

1) What in your opinion is "masculinist culture" and can you identity some "masculinist values"?

"Woman should be barefoot and pregnant in the kitchen." The "boys club" in a work or play environment. Men that fall in this group would not involve their woman in any decision that would have a major impact in their lives i.e. financial, home, work or play. In a work environment, they only tolerate woman who hold down menial jobs.

2) Is it a concern in your work (current and or historic) environment. If so, why?

In the past it has been very difficult to ensure that I get recognized for my opinions and ideas. It meant that I had to work harder, longer and smarter than men on a lower level from me in order to stay on top. In some cases this is still a problem within my current work environment. Both "Companies C and D" would far prefer to hear an opinion or have interaction from/with a man. It has been difficult to make them listen and in many cases escalation (to the highest people) of a problem had to happen, as they tend to try and ignore me. I have given very strong opinions about the way the project/s should have been run in the past that were ignored, only to find that 6 months later a decision has been made based on what I said BUT it has come from a "man". I find this emotionally frustrating but I refuse to allow it to beat me. I do not enjoy the politics of the work environment but they have to be played in order to survive.

3) Have you any personal experiences that you would like to share.

In the past I have been forced to have men work for me that earned more than I did. The basis for this is that a man is the "bread winner", unlike me of course who was the single parent of 2 children who also assisted a parent financially. Men that were promoted before me but did not have a single deliverable to their name but they did belong to the "boys club". At the 1st company I worked for, the highest a woman could get was Store Manager! At one stage, I belonged to a company where women were not allowed into the social club at all!

4) How does "masculinist values" impede on the quality of your working life and in your career ambitions?

It has impacted my back pocket, which directly influences the quality of life for my family. It also made studying a lot more difficult, due to the time factor (working longer hours to be noticed). It has made it far more difficult for me to move up the ranks as quickly as a man, which could have been very demotivating if I had allowed it to get to me.

5) What changes (if any) would you make to your organisational culture to better manage gender diversity?

There should be no hidden agendas (however this is wishful thinking as all work environment have this). I think that "our company" is going a long way to try and make changes in the area BUT they must not make the same mistake that has historically been made with men. "Our company" has appointed some really to notch women execs BUT there are a few that should not have the job, as they do not have an originally thought in their heads. In order for this company to survive, it requires direction from a strong leader, as well as managing it's clients and suppliers professionally i.e. signed contracts, penalties and rewards, proper project management & decent career management/guidance etc.

6) Comments

I think I have said more that enough already.

Interview 3 - Single female - Consultant in the IT industry

1) What in your opinion are "masculinist values" ?

1. Valuing men over women (eg. paying them more);
2. Placing whites at the top of a hierarchy (eg. assigning a white woman a more responsible role than a black man - without due consideration to their respective skills) and
3. Valuing masculine qualities over feminine ones (eg. never focus on how your employees are feeling - pretend that feelings have no place at all in the workplace).

2) Is it a concern in your work environment. If so, why?

Not especially because I am happy working for my boss. But if I want to get busy analysing the department as a whole I would get completely depressed because I think there is a severe communication breakdown and I think this has to do with my point (3) above. I think being able to perceive what's going on beneath the surface is a feminine value - whether displayed in men or women.

3) Have you had any personal experiences that you would like to share ?

A few years ago I had an unpleasant experience of harassment at work. A male contractor made unwelcome sexual comments to me and I felt powerless. That being said I did receive support from my male boss at the time. Both this boss and the male boss I currently have don't support sexism at all.

4) How does "masculinist values" impede on the quality of your working life and in your career ambitions?

I am in a very fortunate position at work. My male boss is usually sensitive to gender bias and my working life is enhanced working for him. However, I cannot say the same for our Head of Department. He'll do things like ink at me in a fatherly way after an exchange - completely unconscious of what he's doing.

5) What changes (if any) would you make to your organisational culture to better manage gender diversity?

This is a difficult question to answer because I don't think people learn things that don't fit their familiar frame of reference - unless they are open-minded and willing. Therefore I am cynical about implementing changes - those who most need to change their values most probably won't. In an ideal world I would screen managers much more closely. Good managers in my opinion have fundamental respect for people - certainly not a quality that is measurable in a questionnaire and also not something that will be picked up by an interviewer necessarily. So I acknowledge that while it's difficult to pick good managers - this is the key to building a working environment filled with satisfied employees.

6) Comments

When I think of patriarchy (a fatherly attitude expressed in the idea that a man knows how to run a department and women's ideas are not as important) and sexism (eg. paying women less) at work; I am aware that my experience is heavily dependent on the boss that I work for - whether man or woman. A woman can be masculinist in her approach to other women and the way she regards men (as superior) as any man.

Interview 4 - Single male - Manager in the IT industry

1) What in your opinion are “masculinist values” ?

Seeing the world from a male perspective and as a result implementing an unfair world

2) Is it a concern in your work environment. If so, why?

No, there is strong female presence in the department, outnumbering the males.

3) Have you had any personal experiences that you would like to share ?

No

4) How does “masculinist values” impede on the quality of your working life and in your career ambitions?

It doesn't

5) What changes (if any) would you make to your organisational culture to better manage gender diversity?

A more equal gender distribution across the department.

6) Comments

Sexist attitudes are mistakenly taken to mean a prejudice of men against women. Although this is the prevailing attitude, it must not be forgotten that the reverse is also true. For example, it is incredibly difficult for men to obtain custody of their children and almost impossible for men to adopt their own natural children

Interview 5 - Single female - Consultant in the IT industry

1) What in your opinion are “masculinist values” ?

Values pertaining only to men, taking no account of how women's values might differ.

2) Is it a concern in your work environment. If so, why?

Yes, male managers are seen as assertive, women managers as aggressive when they display exactly the same

characteristics. General assumption is that senior managers / professors must be male.

3) Have you had any personal experiences that you would like to share?

Have seen the above assumption in action

4) How does “masculinist values” impede on the quality of your working life and in your career ambitions?

Male senior management tends not to confer with or negotiate with women managers. They are still not really given equal status in practice, although in theory they are equal to their male counterparts.

5) What changes (if any) would you make to your organisational culture to better manage gender diversity?

There has never been a woman vice-chancellor, more women in senior positions do not necessarily make an immediate difference but perhaps effective top female management might change the impression of the “old boys club” where decisions are taken in all-male clubs and on the golf course !

6) Comments

Masculinist values impact female employees in two major areas, namely, psychologically and career-wise.

Survey Results

The survey conducted focused on adult white males between the ages of 20 - 37. The culture was predominantly Afrikaans.

The above survey found that more the 50% of the males interviewed preferred the woman in their lives to be a housewife.

25% saw them as equals and 25% believed that a woman could pursue most careers limited from the careers that involved physical labour.

The invisible sexism was seen again in the 25% that said a woman was equal when asked Question 2 they said they would definitely greet a woman verbally and not with a hand shake. That I believed was a ‘guy thing’

95% of the males interviewed preferred females superiors because they believed that females are easily manipulated then male superiors.

95% also believed that female world leaders did not get the same respect as male leaders in the same position. Coupled with the latter point they also believed that women in power were far too emotional and sensitive even if they did not show it.

50% of the males interviewed believed that 12% of the world's population had female leaders and this figure will soon grow to 40% and not more than that, they will never lead more than the male reason being they have secondary and primary tasks of being mothers and wife's.

Well needless to say I was not impressed yet I have grown in my field nothing has changed except I have learned to ignore the comments.

Conclusion

Masculinist values have an adverse effect on female employees and their ability to contribute to the organisation as much under different circumstances is hindered. This is a serious concern in modern organisations as there has been an apparent realisation of the magnitude of the positive difference that female employees can make in an organisation. Recently more and more women are being promoted to senior positions. The masculine culture that once existed so prominently during prehistoric times is fading fast. Perceptions are changing as well. More and more men don't mind the woman being the breadwinner of the household. Women are being taken more seriously and their opinions are being heard and actioned. Daily, new legislation is being introduced to better deal with sexual harassment in the work and to stop female employees from being exploited and or verbal/physical abuse.

“Look out Tarzan, Here comes Jane”

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